
1-butanol production from polluted industrialised District using *Synechococcus elongatus* as alternative to gasoline: Comparison with Clean Regions

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Abstract In this study it was aimed to produce 1-butanol from CO₂ trapping from the polluted industrial regions using *S. elongatus*. The air from two polluted industrial districts (Aliağa and Urla) was trapped with an air pump and it was purified by passing the gas from two bacteria namely *Nitrosomonas sp.* and *Azotobacter sp.* located and grown in two separate adsorbent pads sealed with glass reactors. By consuming of O₂ and N₂ gases the remaining gas is CO₂ and it was used to produce 1-butanol by Cyanobacteria. The effects of CO₂ concentrations, O₂ level, NO₃-N⁻¹, SO₄⁻³, pH, temperature and retention time, on the 1- butanol yield were investigated. 1- butanol and CO₂ concentrations were measured in GC-MS. The enzymes catalyzing the 1-butanol production (acetyl-CoA acetyltransferase (AtoB), 3-hydroxybutyryl-CoA dehydrogenase (Hbd), crotonase (Crt), trans-2-enoyl-CoA reductase (Ter) and bifunctional aldehyde alcohol dehydrogenase (AdhE2)) were measured in a spectrophotometer. The Cyanobacteria was growth in B-11 media and the biochemical test were performed for the characterization of *S. elongatus*. Nowadays, the cost of 1 liter gasoline is 1.60 Euro while the cost of the 1-butanol produced is only 0.66 Euro. The maximum 1- butanol yield was 98% when the A to B and 3-Hbd concentrations were around 0.7X10⁻¹ and 2X10⁻¹ mg/l in Aliağa industrial district while low 1-butanol yield (66%) was obtained in non polluted Urla Region at pH=7.1, after 20 days of incubation at 30 °C.

Keywords 1-butanol, biofuel, Cyanobacteria, *S. elongatus*

1. Introduction

Although carbon dioxide in air was in minor level (between 0 – 0.03 %) it's concentration elavated significantly in municipal metropollutant areas and industrial regions. The carbon dioxide concentration in the atmosphere increase 2-3 ppm in every year as a result of burning in fosil fuels. Sometimes the carbon dioxide levels in industrail regions can reach to 600-700 ppm [1]. 80–85 % of atmospheric carbon dioxide produced by fosil fuels (petroleum, coal and natural gas), 15-20 % of the atmospheric carbon dioxide originated from the respiration of humans and some organisms and from the microorganisms transforming the organic compounds. The pollution increase contionusly as the energy source was utilized. The global studies concern to reduce the carbon dioxide level to the minimum limit (450 ppm) by reducing the CO₂ emissions to 50-80 % in year 2050. 1-butanol is a primary alcohol with a four carbon structure and with a chemical formula of C₄H₉OH. Its molecular weight İs 74.1216 g/mol, it is colorless and have the same density as water. 1-Butanol is considered as a potential fuel substitute to displace gasoline. The energy density of 1-butanol (27 MJ/L) is higher than that of ethanol (21 MJ/L) and closer to that of gasoline (32 MJ/L). In addition, its low hygroscopicity and compatibility with current infrastructure make 1-butanol an attractive fuel substitute [2]. 1-butanol can be produced by synthesis the butyryl-CoA from acetyl-CoA in a

pathway. 1-butanol formation pathway consists of five enzymes namely acetyl-CoA acetyltransferase (AtoB), 3-hydroxybutyryl-CoA dehydrogenase (Hbd), crotonase (Crt), trans-2-enoyl-CoA reductase (Ter) and bifunctional aldehyde alcohol dehydrogenase (AdhE2) [3]. The development of new technologies for production of alternative fuel became necessary to circumvent finite petroleum resources, associate rising costs, and environmental concerns due to rising fossil fuel CO₂ emissions. Several alternatives have been proposed to develop a sustainable industrial society and reduce greenhouse emissions. The idea of biological conversion of CO₂ to fuel and chemicals is receiving increased attention. In particular, the direct conversion of CO₂ with solar energy to biofuel by photosynthetic microorganisms such as microalgae and cyanobacteria has several advantages compared to traditional biofuel production from plant biomass. Several emerging technologies are being implemented in order to overcome the problem of greenhouse gas (GHG) pollution and replace fossil fuels by promoting viable production of liquid fuels such as fatty acid esters (biodiesel) Conversion of CO₂ for the synthesis of chemicals by photosynthetic organisms is an attractive target for establishing independence from fossil reserves. Direct conversion of CO₂ to bio-based fuels and chemicals has emerged as a significant thrust to address the energy and environmental concerns caused by over-reliance on fossil fuels and the increasing level of atmospheric CO₂. Cyanobacteria are photoautotrophic bacteria that utilize sunlight as their energy source and CO₂ as their carbon source. Because they have adapted or can acclimate to diverse growth environments, they can serve as “photo-bioreactors” for the production of renewable biofuels and green chemicals [4]. Here we report the photosynthetic production of 1-butanol which is an energy-dense fuel molecule, from CO₂ in the genetically engineered cyanobacterium *Synechococcus elongatus*.

In this study it was aimed to produce 1-butanol from CO₂ trapped from two different regions using *S.elongatus*. The air from was trapped from a non-polluted region (Urla-İzmir Turkey) and from a polluted industrial district (Aliğa-İzmir Turkey). The effects of increasing CO₂, O₂, NO₃-N⁻¹, SO₄⁻³ concentrations, temperature, retention time and pH levels on the 1- butanol production from CO₂ by *S.elongatus* were investigated. 1- butanol and CO₂ concentrations were measured in GC-MS. The enzymes catalyzing the 1- butanol production (acetyl-CoA acetyltransferase (AtoB), 3-hydroxybutyryl-CoA dehydrogenase (Hbd), crotonase (Crt), trans-2-enoyl-CoA reductase (Ter) and bifunctional aldehyde alcohol dehydrogenase (AdhE2) were monitored. The addition of plasmid on 1-butanol production was investigated. A cost analysis was performed.

2. Material and Methods

2.1 Microorganisms isolated and used in this study

In this study, Photosynthetic cyanobacteria *S. elongatus* was isolated from Urla and Aliğa Bays in İzmir Turkey.

2.2 Culture Medium and Conditions

All *S. elongatus* cultures were grown on BG-11 (1.5 g NaNO₃, 0.036 g CaCl₂, 0.006 g ferric ammonium citrate, 0.001 g EDTA, 0.04 g K₂HPO₄, 0.075 g MgSO₄, 0.02 g Na₂CO₃, 1000 × trace mineral (2.86 g H₃BO₃, 1.81 g MnCl₂·4H₂O, 0.22 g ZnSO₄·7H₂O, 0.390 g Na₂MoO₄·2H₂O, 0.0790 g CuSO₄·5H₂O, 0.0494 g Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O)[5]. The pH of the liquid was adjusted to 7.1 by adding 1 mM NaHCO₃ and 100 mM KOH to the BG-11 medium. All *S. elongatus* strains were cultured in BG-11 medium in a shaking incubator at 120 rpm. Cultures were grown under 60 W light condition at 30 °C. Under laboratory conditions to the 250 ml sterile glass bottles containing 100 ml of BG-11 liquid medium 100 ml of isolated *S. elongatus* culture was added. To the each culture purified CO₂ gas trapped from the Aliğa and Urla regions were given between hours 10.00-18.00 in a day five times at a flow rate of 0.083 m³/sec during 30 days.

2.3 Purification of CO₂ from the trapped air

The atmospheric gas trapped by vacuum pumps from the Urla And Aliğa atmosphere regions and it is were stored in the polyethylene air bags (Figures 1 and 2). The atmospheric gas was passed from an absorbant ped containing *Azotobacter* (Figure 3) In this step the N₂ gas present in the air samples was eliminated since this bacteria used N₂

gas for growth. The *Azotobacter sp.* medium consisted from 08% K_2HPO_4 ; 0.02% KH_2PO_4 , 0.02% $MgSO_4$ 0.01% $CaSO_4$; 0.0015% $FeSO_4/7H_2O$; 0.00025% g $NaMoO_3$ and 0.5% sucrose. Then the remaining gas was passed from an absorbant ped containing *Nitrosomonas sp.* bacteria. This bacteria used the O_2 in the air (Figure 3). As *Nitrosomonas* medium Medium A, Medium B, Medium A-Z and A-2 Trace medium were used. A medium consisting of $(NH_4)_2SO_4$ 0.1 g; K_2HPO_4 0.1 g; $NaCl$ 0.2 g; $MgSO_4.7H_2O$ 0.05 g; $FeCl_3$ trace; $CaCO_3$ 1.0 g and tap water 100 ml. Medium B was made up as follows: $NaCl$ 0.3 g; $MgSO_4.7H_2O$ 0.14 g; $FeSO_4.7H_2O$ 0.03 g AND $(NH_4)_2SO_4$ 0.66 g. They are dissolved in 90 ml distilled water. The 'A-2' trace element mixture contains $LiSO_4$ 0.01 g; $CuSO_4$ 0.02 g; $ZnSO_4$ 0.02 g; H_3BO_4 0.22 g; $Al_2(SO_4)$ 0.02 g; $SnCl_2$ 0.01 g; $MnCl_2$ 0.14 g; $NiCl_2$ 0.02 g; $CoSO_4$ 0.02 g; $TiCl_4$ (15% solution) 0.13 ml; KI 0.01 g; KBr 0.01 g and distilled water, 360 ml. As a result the air was purified from N_2 and O_2 and contained %99.9 CO_2 with the exception of some nox gases.

2.4 The Identification of *S.elongatus* PCC 7942

In order to identify the *S.elongatus* cyanobacteria isolated from the atmosphere its dimensions were measured under microscope. Then its growth in urea, ammonia, nitrite and nitrat media tests were performed. Bradford test was performed to determine the protein content.

2.5 Measurement of 1-butanol

1-butanol was measured in an Agilent GC-MS 7890-A system with flame ionization detector and DB-FFAP capillary column. 1-Butanol standard of 0.001% v/v was used and dilutions were performed. Helium gas was used as the carrier gas. The injector and detector temperatures were maintained at 250 °C. Injection volume was 1 μ L. The GC oven temperature was initially held at 40 °C for 4 min and then raised to 250 °C. Column flow rate was 3 ml/min. 1-Butanol typically had a retention time of 2.483 min.

2.6 CO_2 measurement in HPLC

For CO_2 quantification; 1 ml of gas was drawn by 1MR-VLL-GT FL0D syringe. Helium gas was used as the carrier gas. The injector and detector temperatures were maintained at 40 °C. Injection volume was 1 μ L. The GC oven temperature was initially held at 40 °C for 4 min then it increased to 250 °C [6].

2.7 Enzyme Activity Measurements

3-hydroxybutyryl-CoA dehydrogenase (Hbd) activity measurement: Hbd activity was measured in a spectrophotometer AQUAMETC by monitoring the decrease in absorbance at 340 nm, which corresponded to consumption of NADH [7]. 3-hydroxybutyryl-CoA dehydrogenase (Hbd) measurement: Hbd activity was measured in a spectrophotometer AQUAMETC by monitoring the decrease in absorbance at 340 nm, which corresponded to consumption of NADH [7]. Bradford protein measurement: By taken into consideration the blue colour production with interaction of Coomassie brilliant blue and proteins at a adsorbans of 595 nm as measured in an AQUAMATE (Helios Aquamate) spectrophotometer.

Dissolved oxygene was measured in a WTW dissolved oxygene meter. The lighth power was measured by a luminometer (OASIS). Additional pure CO_2 was added with an CO_2 tube with a purity of 99.9%.

2.8 Plasmid addition

2 μ g pAM2991 plazmit-DNA was transferred to the *S. elongatus* grown in BG-11 media containing 3.4×10^2 cell/ml in 2 days incubations in dark. pAM2991 plasmid is consisting from neutral region – I (NSI), target vector and P_{trc} initial primer. It contains the genes namely asetil-CoA asetiltransferaz (atoB) and aldehyd/alkol dehidrojenaz (adhE2) for 1- butanol productions.

2.9 Environmental Factors affecting the number of cyanobacteria, produced 1-butanol concentration and 1-butanol_{produced}/CO_{2utilized} yield

The effect of excess CO₂ concentration on 1-butanol yield was researched by passing of CO₂ gas with a purity of 99.99% at a flow rate of 0.013 m³/sec from a CO₂ tube at concentration varying between 10, 20 and 30 mg/l and compared with the 1-butanol production from the trapped CO₂ concentration (9.8 mg/l). The effect of dissolved oxygen on the yield of 1-butanol production was investigated. The DO concentration was increased from 0.2 mg/l from which is found in the trapped air after purification to 0.4, 0.5, 2 and 4 mg/l. Then, the effect of increasing NO₃-N concentrations (0.5 mg/l, 1, 1.5 and 2 mg/l) on the 1-butanol yields was investigated. Effects of increasing SO₄⁻³ concentrations (0.5 mg/l, 1, 1.5 and 3 mg/l) and the effects of increasing temperatures (15°C, 30, 40, 50 and 65°C) on 1-butanol productions were studied. Furthermore, the effects of Ph (4, 7, 8 and 9) and retention times (25 days, 40, 55 and 75 days) on 1-butanol yields was studied.

The effect of addition of pAM2991 plasmid to each *S. elongatus* culture was evaluated. Plasmid pEL5 was constructed by insertion of atoB and adhE2 enzymes into pAM2991 between the BamHI and NotI sites, under an IPTG-inducible promoter P_{trc}. *S. elongatus* strains. The genes were transformed by incubating cells at mid-log phase with 2 µg of plasmid DNA overnight in dark. The culture was then spread on BG-11 plates and 20 µg/ml spectinomycin was added into BG-11 agar plates.

2.10 Calculation of 1-butanol production yields versus CO₂ utilized

The calculation of the yield for 1-butanol concentration produced from utilized CO₂ were done via the formula given in (1), and the yield percentages were calculated via the formula given in (2). In the calculations, the theoretical value of 1-butanol_{produced}/CO_{2used} is 0, 25.

$$\text{Yield (Y)} = \frac{1\text{-butanol produced}}{\text{CO}_2\text{utilized}} \quad (1)$$

$$\% \text{ Yield (\% Y)} = \frac{1\text{-butanolproduced}/\text{CO}_2\text{utilized}}{\text{Theoric } 1\text{-butanolproduced}/\text{CO}_2\text{utilized}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Identification of *S. elongatus* PCC 7942 Cyanobacteria

The identification of *S. elongatus* cyanobacteria was done at the end of 30 days (t = 30°C, pH = 7.1, Eh = 120 mV, Light conditions = 60 W, CO₂ flow rate = 0,083 m³/sec). The dimensions of the *S. elongatus* cells differed from 1,5 up to 2,0 µm of length with a width of 0,4-6 µm as is reported in literature studies. In the ammonia test the reproduction of blurry exhibited that ammonia was used by *S. elongatus* at 28°C which is this a positive result given in the literature (Table 1). In the nitrat test *S. elongatus* produced blur by using nitrat reductase enzymes nitrat medium. For nitrit test *S. elongatus* used the reductase enzyme and utilized the nitrit and converted to nitrate. On the other hand, *S. elongatus* use urea and turns them into ammonia and caused blur in tubes (Table 1). Bradford test was done at the end of 30 days in order to determine the protein amount of *S. elongatus* (Table 1).

Table 1: Identification of *S. elongatus* cyanobacteria

Studies	Cyanobacteria Sizes		Number of Cyanobacteria (colony/ml)	Ammonia Test	Nitrate Test	Nitrite Test	Urea Test	Bradford Test Protein Concen. (µg/ml)	CO ₂ concen. (mg/l)
	lengths (µm)	widths (µm)							
Aliağa	3 - 18	0.6 – 5	10000	Blured - Positive (+)	Blured – Positive (+)	Blured - Positive (+)	Blured - Positive (+)	78	178
Aliağa	2 - 17	0.5 – 5	9800	Blured - Positive (+)	Blured – Positive (+)	Blured - Positive (+)	Blured - Positive (+)	75	177

Urla	1 - 16	0.4 – 4	7000	Blured - Positive (+)	Blured – Positive (+)	Blured - Positive (+)	Blured - Positive (+)	57	118
Urla	1 - 15	0.4 – 3.8	6900	Blured - Positive (+)	Blured – Positive (+)	Blured - Positive (+)	Blured - Positive (+)	44	117

According to the results obtained from the biochemical tests all isolated Cyanobacteria in Aliaga and Urla are *S. elongatus*. The maximum *S. elongatus* cells reached in the Aliaga region which in this region the Measured CO₂ concentration are at the higher level. The *S. elongatus* numbers reduced in Urla Region are lower than that Aliaga Region since in this region the CO₂ concentrations were at the lowest level. Therefore, from the low CO₂ concentration (mole) the produced of 1mol 1-butanol will be lower. In other words, from the CO₂ the proced butanol yields will be high. On the other hand the maximum protein concncentration was observed at the *S. elongatus* cells isolated from Aliaga Region.

3.2 Purification of trapped air from O₂ and N₂ gases

The air with a flow rate of 0.083 m³/sec was passed from an adsorbent containing *N. europaea* for 5 minutes in every half an hour time for 7 days tances of. The number of *N.europaea* was 2x10² /ml and the flow rate of O₂ gas in the air was 0.055 m³/sec (Table 2). The N₂ gas in the rest of the air was removed by passing the remaining air from an adsorbant containing *Azotobacter sp.* with a flow rate of 0.015 m³/sec containing 1x10²/ml *A. vinelandii*. The rest of the air was used by *S.elongatus* PCC 7942 in production of 1-butanol which contains pure CO₂ at a flow rate of 0.013 m³/ sec (Table 2).

Table 2: Result of purification process that captured in the CO₂-rich air in the polluted area

	Culture Properties		Cultural Properties of organisms growing in adsorbant pads with the gases trapping from the atmosphere	
	<i>N. europaea</i>	<i>A. vinelandii</i>	<i>N. europaea</i>	<i>A. vinelandii</i>
Number of <i>N. europaea</i> (number/ml)	5x10 ⁵	-	2x10 ³	-
Number of <i>A. vinelandii</i> (number/ml)	-	3x10 ⁴	-	1x10 ³
Flow of dissolved O₂ (m³/sec)	0.04	-	0.055	-
Flow of N₂ (m³/sec)	-	0.038	-	0.015

3.3. CO₂ utilization By *S. elongatus*

Water, N, P and CO₂ play an important role in the growing of photosynthetic cynobacteria [4]. Murray et al., (1982) [8] determined that cynobacteria grow faster in high CO₂ concentration while Fu et al. (2007) [9] determined that the more CO₂ concentration increase the photosynthesis in cyanobacteria. In this study it was determined that *S. elongatus* remove more CO₂ in Aliaga industry district where the CO₂ concetrations are high in this polluted area (Table 3). The CO₂ concentrations are low in Urla region since this domain is a seaside in which the tourism activities are high. Therefore the CO₂ levels are low and the utilized CO₂ is low in Urla which not a polluted area. To produce 1 mol 1-butanol with Calvin-Benson-Bassham cycle, 6 mol CO₂ is required. This amount of CO₂ is calculated with the numbers of glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate (G3P) and NAD(P)H which are necessary for 1-butanol production. 1 mol G3P availability from 3 mol CO₂ is required for 6 mol NADPH. Consequently, 2 mol G3P is required to produce 1 mol 1-butanol. Thus, 6 mol CO₂ is required to produce 1 mol of 1-butanol [10]. Cyanobacteria fix carbon to provide the skeletons needed to assimilate N into amino acids and build protein and cellular biomass; fixed carbon can also be used to accumulate carbohydrate storage products (carbohydrate ballasting) in order to make the cell heavier during buoyancy regulation.

Table 3: CO₂ utilization by *S. elongatus*

Studies	The initial concentration of CO ₂ (mg/L)	After 30 days concentration of CO ₂ (mg/L)	Utilized concentration of CO ₂ (mg/L)
Aliaga	178.7	25.7	153
Aliaga	178.2	38.2	140
Urla	118.5	30.5	80
Urla	118.12	20.82	83.3

3.4. Effects of environmental factors on the 1-Butanol production from CO₂

3.4. 1. Effect of excess CO₂ concentrations on 1- butanol production

The CO₂ concentrations in Aliaga and Urla regions were measured around 178 and 118 mg/l, respectively. As the the CO₂ concentrations were increased from 178 mg/L to 188 and to 198 mg/l by addition of pure CO₂ gas the 1-butanol productions increased from 153 mg/l to 176 and to 185 mg/l in Aliaga region. As the CO₂ concentration were increased from 118 mg/l to 128 and to 138 mg/l by the additions of 10 and 20 mg/l pure CO₂ gas. Further increase of pure CO₂ concentration to 30 mg/l the 1- butanol production decreased significantly in both regions. This showed that an optimum CO₂ level can stimulate the 1- butanol production via photosynthesis. *S. elongatus* use sunlight as an energy source, and recycle CO₂, making them an advantageous platform for the production of 1-butanol. *Synechococcus* is a genus of unicellular marine cyanobacteria that are found in both freshwater and marine water environments. *Synechococcus* exhibits several pathways for carbon metabolism. Its main pathway for carbon metabolism under photoautotrophic conditions involves glycolysis, pentose phosphate shunt, incomplete TCA cycle, and photophosphorylation [11]. Under mixotrophic conditions involving either glucose or acetate, these compounds are incorporated as organic carbon compounds. Yan et al., [12] showed in 2010 that glucose is metabolized through the main pathway and the CO₂ released through respiration and fixed by photosynthesis (Calvin cycle). ATP is produced via three metabolic pathways: substrate phosphorylation, oxidative phosphorylation, and photophosphorylation. Substrate phosphorylation is the production of ATP by the donation of a phosphoryl group (PO₃) from the metabolites in all reaction pathways. In oxidative phosphorylation, which is carried out using an electron transport chain, ATP is generated using either NADH or FADH with low O₂ as the terminal electron acceptor. Photophosphorylation uses light energy to convert ADP to ATP through photosynthetic reactions.

Table 4: Effect of excess CO₂ concentrations on 1- butanol production

Region	CO ₂ mg/L (178 Aliaga and 118 Urla)	CO ₂ addition- 10 mg/L	CO ₂ addition- 20 mg/L	CO ₂ addition- 30 mg/L
Aliaga – 1-BT (mg/l)	153	176	185	120
Aliaga1-BT (mg/l)	140	159	165	100
Urla 1-BT (mg/l)	124.38	132	167	119
Urla1-BT (mg/l)	103.3	121	142	90

3.4.2. Effect of NO₃-N concentrations 1-butanol productions

The trapped air after purification has no NO₃-N concentration. As the NO₃-N concentration was increased from 1 to 2 mg/l the 1- butanol production reached to a maximum (178 and 140 mg/l, respectively in the *S. elongatus* isolated from Aliaga and in Urla regions) in both domains (Table 5).

Table 5: Effect of NO₃-N concentrations 1-butanol productions

District	NO ₃ -N conc. 0 mg/l	NO ₃ -N conc. 1 mg/l	NO ₃ -N conc. 2 mg/l	NO ₃ -N conc. 4 mg/l	NO ₃ -N conc. 5 mg/l
Aliaga – 1-BT (mg/l)	153	167	178	110	90
Aliaga1-BT (mg/l)	140	155	167	100	89
Urla 1-BT (mg/l)	110.5	132	140	90	70
Urla1-BT (mg/l)	101.3	121	142	90	68

Further increase of NO₃-N concentration decrease significantly the 1- butanol production. As NO₃-N is also a charged molecule it's transported into the cell via active transport. Cyanobacteria use two different transport systems. Most freshwater species, including *Anabaena*, *Synechocystis* and *Gloebacter*, use the high affinity ATP-binding cassette (ABC) transporter NrtABCD [13]. Most marine species (*Synechococcus* and others) take up NO₃ - and NO₂- via the major facilitator superfamily transporter NrtP, also a high-affinity transporter [13]. Some species also have a NO₂- specific transporter NIT [14]. Nitrate uptake is tightly regulated by the external concentration of NH₄⁺; when NH₄⁺ becomes available, cells cease NO₃ - uptake and switch to use NH₄⁺ which is preferred. This process is regulated at the level of NO₃- uptake [15]. In addition, CO₂-fixation (regulated by irradiance) is required to maintain active NO₃ - uptake, a regulatory link that ensures that the product of NO₃ - reduction (ammonium) can be incorporated into carbon skeletons [13]. Reduction of NO₃ - to NH₄⁺ is a two-step process catalyzed by the enzymes nitrate reductase (NR) and nitrite reductase (NiR). The power for the reduction reaction, in the form of 2 electrons for NR and 6 electrons for NiR, is provided by F_o via PSI providing a strong link between the light reactions and NO₃- use by the cell [13]. In cyanobacteria, the genes encoding NR, narB, and Nir, nirA, and the NO₃ - transporter NrtP, are typically clustered in the same operon. An operon is a unit that tells the cells to transcribe a sequence of genes simultaneously. In cyanobacteria, the transcription of operons associated with metabolism is tightly regulated by the transcription factor NtcA.

3.4.3. Effect of Dissolved Oxygen on 1-butanol production

The dissolved oxygen (DO) concentration was measured around 0.01 and 0.03 mg/l in trapped air after purificant in both Urla and Aliaga regions. The addition of do effect on 1-butanol production was investigated in both regions. Increasing of DO concentration to 0.4 and 0.5 mg/l affected slightly the 1- butanol productions in both regions (Table 6). Increasing of do concentrations to 2 and to 4 mg/l slightly decreased the 1-butanol productions. The optimum do for maximum 1-butanol production was found to be 0.5 mg/l. Samuel et al., (2014) [16] found that with the increase of dissolved O₂ concentration from 0.01 mg/l to 0.05 mg/l, the number of cyanobacteria, produced 1- butanol concentrations and 1-butanol_{produced}/CO_{2used} yields increased. On the conducted studies, the number of cyanobacterias grown under the anaerobic strict conditions decreased compared to low do (0.05 mg/l) concentrations. As *S. elongatus* are naturally adapted to the low concentrations of atmospheric oxygen [17]; however, in the photosystem II, the lack of oxygen blocks plastoquinone that is an electron carrier [2]. In addition to this, high O₂ and CO₂ levels can inhibit their growth.

Table 6: Effect of Dissolved Oxygen on 1-butanol production

Region	0.01 -0.03 mg/l in trapped air	0.4 mg/l	0.5 mg/l	2 mg/l	4 mg/l
Aliaga – 1-BT (mg/l)	153	156	163	145	120
Aliaga1-BT (mg/l)	140	145	153	145	120
Urla 1-BT (mg/l)	124.38	126	138	115	118
Urla1-BT (mg/l)	103.3	107	115	98	98

3.4.4. Effect of SO_4^{2-} concentration on 1- butanol production

The trapped and purified air did not contain SO_4^{2-} . Addition of SO_4^{2-} concentration from 0.5 to 1.00 mg/l increased the 1- butanol production. 3 mg/l SO_4^{2-} decrease the 1- butanol production (Table 7). The optimum SO_4^{2-} concentration for maximum 1- butanol production was found to be 1 mg/l. Yang et al. (2015) [18] found 40% more growth with the addition of 0,0361 g/L $MgSO_4$ to the BG-11 media and mentioned that SO_4^{2-} is a basic component necessary for the growth of *S. elongatus*. However, they emphasized that increasing of SO_4 concentrations did not increase the growth of *S. elongatus* PCC 7942 more than 20%.

Table 7: Effect of SO_4^{2-} concentration on 1- butanol production

	0 mg/l	0.5 mg/l	1 mg/l	1.5 mg/l	3 mg/l
Aliağa – 1-BT (mg/l)	153	158	164	163	120
Aliağa1-BT (mg/l)	140	146	158	157	130
Urla 1-BT (mg/l)	124.38	129	143	120	100
Urla 1-BT (mg/l)	104	110	143	100	98

3.4.5. Effect of pH on 1- butanol production

For maximum 1-butanol productions the optimum pH was found to be around 7.0. Acidic and alkaline conditions decrease the photosynthesis of CO_2 to 1- butanol in both *S. elongatus* types from Aliağa and Urla regions (Table 8). At basic pH the growth of cyanobacteria is limited and the produced 1-butanol concentrations and 1-butanol_{produced}/ CO_{2used} yields decreased. Rippka et al. (1979) [5] found that maximum growth in BG-11 medium for *S. elongatus* PCC 7942 was observed at a pH of 7.1.

Table 8: Effect of pH on 1- butanol production

	pH pH= 7.1	pH pH=4.0	pH pH=9.0	pH pH=13
Aliağa – 1-BT (mg/l)	153	45	38	134
Aliağa1-BT (mg/l)	140	40	36	100
Urla 1-BT (mg/l)	124.38	34	26	98
Urla1-BT (mg/l)	103.3	29	20	78

3.4.6. Effect of temperature on 1- butanol productions

At low temperature the *S. elongatus* was not effectively grew and could not produce effectively 1- butanol since at low temperatures the metabolic activities decreased (Table 9). At high temperatures the protein content of *S. elongatus* and the enzymes exhibiting inhibitions resulting in decrease in enzyme activities (Table 9). The optimum temperature for maximum 1-butanol production was found to be 40°C. Water temperatures have increased globally over the last few decades as a result of global warming [19]. This indicates that a doubling in cyanobacterial growth rates occurs with an increase in temperature from 20-27°C. From increasing *S. elongatus* cells more 1- butanol will be produced. Kajiwara et al., (1997) [20] found that the growth ratio of *S. elongatus* generally continues to increase with the increasing temperature until it is reached to an optimum temperature. The temperature highly affects its trapping of CO_2 , holding the nutrients and cellular chemical components in *S. elongatus* [21]. For the maximum growth *S. elongatus* cyanobacteria, has been always cultivated at a stable temperature of 30°C.

Table 9: Effect of temperature on 1- butanol productions

	30 °C	40 °C	15 °C	50°C
Aliağa – 1-BT (mg/l)	153	154	143	125
Aliağa1-BT (mg/l)	140	141	128	123
Urla 1-BT (mg/l)	124.38	126	118	114
Urla1-BT (mg/l)	103.3	105	98	76

3.4.7. Effect of retention-incubation time on 1-butanol productions

The optimum 1- butanol production was obtained at an incubation time of 30 days (Table 10). Increasing of retention-incubation times of *S. elongatus* culture did not affect the 1-butanol production. The enzymes catalyzing the photosynthesis are active at 30°C. Further increasing of temperature did not activated the enzymes catalyzing the 1-butanol production from CO₂. By extending the retention period from 15 days to 30 days, an incensement of the number of *S. elongatus* PCC 7942, in 1- butanol concentrations and 1-butanol_{produced}/CO_{2used} yields has been observed by Armbrust et al., (2014) [10]. With the retention period is extended to 45 days, the number of *S. elongatus* PCC 7942, 1- butanol concentration and 1-butanol_{produced}/CO_{2used} yields decreased [10]. The first period for 15 days is the acclimation period of *S. elongatus* while after 45 days was going to the stationary phase. Because residence time is determined by the flushing rate, the direct effect of increased residence time is to decrease the loss rate of cyanobacteria [22]. Studies that report on the effect of residence time suggest that cyanobacterial abundance, cell size and toxin concentration are positively related to increased residence time [22, 23].

Table 10: Effect of retention time on 1- butanol productions

	30 days	40 days	55 days	70 days
Aliağa – 1-BT (mg/l)	153	153	145	60
Aliağa1-BT (mg/l)	140	140	130	50
Urla 1-BT (mg/l)	124,38	124,38	119	45
Urla1-BT (mg/l)	103,3	103,3	96	30

3.5. Enzymes catalyzing the 1-butanol production from CO₂

The enzymes controlling and governing the photosynthesis of CO₂ to produce 1- butanol are HdD, Ter, AdhE2, AtoB and Crt. Among these enzymes Ter and Crt were catalyzing crotonyl-CoA and 3-hydroxybutyryl-CoA, respectively and they are measures at low concentrations (Table 11).

Table 11: Enzym activities during 1 butanol production from CO₂

Enzymes	<i>S. elongatus</i> (µg/l)
Hbd	2 x10 ⁻¹
Ter	3.2 x10 ⁻¹
AdhE2	2.3 x10 ⁻¹
Atob	0.7 X10 ⁻¹
Crt	2.8 x 10 ⁻¹

3.6. Yield Measurements (1-butanol_{productions} / CO_{2utilized})

The maximum yield obtained in this study was 96% and 95% in the *S. elongatus* isolated from the Aliağa Region (Table 11). Lan and Liao (2012) [24] and Shen et al., (2011) [25] found 68-70 % 1-butanol yields by producing 30-42 mg/L 1-butanol from CO₂ using *S. elongatus* PCC 7942 cyanobacteria. In this study, the produced 1- butanol concentrations were around 120-135 in the *S. elongates* cyanobacteria isolated from Aliağa region. Among the studies carried out, the lowest 1- butanol yields was obtained in the *S. elongatus species* isolated from Urla district 1-butanol_{produced}/CO_{2used}.

Table 11: 1-butanol yields from utilized CO₂

Studies	Utilized concentration of CO ₂ (mg/L)	Concentration of 1-butanol (mg/L)	Yield	% Yield
Aliaga	153	133.5	0.167	96.6
Aliaga	140	122.83	0.14	95
Urla	124.38	80.73	0.11	60
Urla	103.3	81.5	0.09	59

3.7. Effect of plasmid addition on 1-butanol production

Plasmid transformation; has been done by carrying the *atoB* and *adhE2* genes in pEL5 plasmid to the genes of *S. elongatus* PCC 7942 via using the recombinant DNA techniques. The pEL5 plasmid DNA has been done with the recombination of *S. elongatus* PCC 7942's neutral zone. Plasmid pEL5 consists of the genes *atoB* and *adhE2*. These plasmids have been used because they include *atoB* and *adhE2* which is necessary to produce 1-butanol from CO₂ via *S. elongatus* PCC 7942. The genes *atoB* and *adhE2* in plasmid pEL5 have been transferred into *S. elongatus* PCC 7942 DNA via BamHI and NotI. areas in pAM2991. pEL5 genotype is an *adhE2* that is resistant to spectinomycin (Spec^R), intended for NSI, Ptrc: *atoB* [2]. After pAM2991 plasmid was transferred to *S. elongatus* a recombination was recorded. PCR photos for *adhE2* (a) and *atoB* (b) genes primers were given in Figure 2 (a) exhibited the acetyl-CoA acetyltransferase (*atoB*) while (b) showed the aldehyd/alcohol dehydrogenaz (*adhE2*).

Figure 2: PCR photos *AdhE2* (a) and *atoB* (b) genes primers: (a) acetyl-CoA acetyltransferase (*atoB*), (b) aldehyde/alcohol dehydrogenase (*adhE2*).

As shown in Table 12, the addition of plasmid to the *S. elongatus* increased significantly 1-butanol production, the number of *S. elongatus*, 1-butanol yields and the *atoB* and *AdHE2* enzymes activities compared to *S. elongatus* without plasmid.

Table 12: Effect of plasmid addition on 1-butanol production

	Without plasmid	With plasm	<i>S. elongatus</i> number/ml with plasm	1-butan. yield (%) with plasm	<i>atoB</i> (µg/l) with plasm	<i>adhE2</i> (µg/l) with plasm
Aliaga – 1-BT (mg/l)	153	189	15000	93	12x10 ⁻¹	9x10 ⁻¹
Aliaga1-BT (mg/l)	140	162	14000	90	12x10 ⁻¹	8x10 ⁻¹
Urla 1-BT (mg/l)	124.38	134	12000	84	9x10 ⁻¹	6x10 ⁻¹

4. Cost analysis

The isolation of *S. elongatus*, labour, chemical costs; purification and electricity costs were recorded as 1.06 Euro to produce 1 liter 1- butanol from 180 mg/l CO₂ trapping from the Tablo 13. In order to produce 10.000 m³ 1- butanol from 1000 g/l CO₂, the cost was calculated as 0.13 Euro. With the addition of plasmid the total cost to produce 10.000 m³ 1-butanol is 0.68 Euro. The produced 1 liter of 1-butanol cost was compared with the gasoline. The produced 1-butanol cost is approximately 3 times lower than 1 liter conventional gasoline.

Table 13: Cost Analysis for 1- butanol production from CO₂

Isolation cost for <i>S. elongatus</i>	0.10 euro
Labour cost	0.06 euro
Electricity	60 W light power: 0.2 euro Illumination for 35 days
CO ₂ purification	0.3 euro
Total cost without plasmid	Total cost : 0.66 Euro/L
Addition of plasmid (0.4 euro)	Total cost: 1.06 euro /L
Total cost without plasmid	0.13 EURO / 10.000 m ³ 1- butanol
Addition of plasmid (0.4 euro)	Total cost: 0.68 euro/10.000 m ³ 1-butanol

Figure 3: Comparison of 1- butanol and gasoline costs

5. Discussion

Rising global energy demands and pressing environmental issues, interest is growing in the production of fuels from renewable resources. Petroleum consumption reached 42.1 quadrillion BTU in the United States in 2015, of which a large majority (71%) was liquid fuel in the transportation sector. Petroleum and natural gas account for 99% of the feed-stocks for chemicals, such as plastics, fertilizers, and pharmaceuticals in the chemical industry. Considering rapidly increasing world population and exhaustion of fossil fuels, the development of sustainable processes for energy and carbon capture to produce fuels and chemicals is crucial for human society. Energy and carbon capture by cyanobacteria is also directed toward mitigating increasing atmospheric CO₂ concentrations. According to the US Energy Information Administration, world energy-related CO₂ emissions in 2006 were 29 billion metric tons, which is an increase of 35% from 1990. Accelerating accumulation of atmospheric CO₂ is not only a result of increased emissions from world growth and intensifying carbon use, but also from a possible attenuation in the efficiency of the world's natural carbon sinks. As a result, atmospheric levels of CO₂ have increased by ~25% over the past 150 years and it has become increasingly important to develop new technologies to

reduce CO₂ emissions. Many creative solutions have been proposed and argued for carbon capture, each with varied environmental side-effects and costs. Sequestration by photosynthetic microorganisms in which CO₂ is biologically converted to valuable chemicals is an important addition to the toolbox for overall capture of CO₂. Photosynthetic microorganisms, including cyanobacteria, are currently being engineered for platforms to convert solar energy to biochemicals renewably. These microorganisms possess many advantages over traditional terrestrial plants with regard to biochemical production. For example, the photosynthetic efficiency of photosynthetic microorganisms is higher than plants, and photosynthetic microorganisms can be cultivated in locations that do not compete with traditional agricultural crops. Cyanobacteria are collectively responsible for almost 50% of global photosynthesis and are found in a wide range of environments. Cyanobacteria have the biochemical machinery required to fix CO₂, but lack the critical components to generate fuels and chemicals efficiently. An increased understanding of cellular systems enables us to construct novel systems using synthetic biology, assembling the components and control systems into new combinations.

At present, the cost of developed biofuel, is still several times lower than that fossil fuels. Future developments in strain selection and engineering, bioreactor design and processing technology then may pave the way for the production of fuels, using the direct conversion approach that can economically compete with their fossil counterparts.

6. Conclusion

The eco-friendly 1-butanol; is an economic alternative fuel, It can be produced by the waste CO₂ from the atmosphere which cause pollution, it is suitable to use as heat, force and alternative motor fuel. From a pollutant a renewable energy (biofuel) was produced.

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